

Tetrathiocarbamato complexes and forced configurations

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Oxovanadium(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes of tetrathiocarbamates of *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-phenylenediamines (OPDTTC, MPDTTC and PPDTTTC) have been synthesized. Cobalt remains in the +2 state and is not spontaneously oxidized to +3 during complexation, which may be attributed to the structural rigidity imposed by the ligands. All the complexes show metal-metal interaction with the exception of oxovanadium(II) complexes, which do not show metal-metal interaction. The copper complexes are found to be diamagnetic indicating a strong metal-metal interaction through the ligand by super-exchange mechanism.

Dithiocarbamates have been studied extensively¹. But tetrathiocarbamates have not been studied extensively. They may possess interesting structural features and biological activities. Therefore, the tetrathiocarbamates have been synthesized from phenylenediamines and their complexes with oxovanadium(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) have been synthesized and characterized.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses (Table 1) suggest that all the complexes correspond to 1 : 1 metal : ligand stoichiometry. The complexes are insoluble in most of the organic solvents and hence the molar conductance for the complexes could not be determined.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the complexes^a

Compd.	Colour	Metal % : Found (Calcd.)	μ_{eff} B.M.
(VO) ₂ (OPDTTC) ₂	Green	15.8 (15.6)	1.93
Co ₂ (OPDTTC) ₂ .(H ₂ O) ₂	Green	17.4 (17.6)	4.66
Ni ₂ (OPDTTC) ₂ .(H ₂ O) ₂	Brown	17.2 (17.5)	2.77
Cu ₂ (OPDTTC) ₂ .(H ₂ O) ₂	Brown	18.9 (18.7)	dia.
(VO) ₂ (MPDTTC) ₂	Green	15.5 (15.6)	1.80
Co ₂ (MPDTTC) ₂ .(H ₂ O) ₂	Green	17.9 (17.6)	4.08
Ni ₂ (MPDTTC) ₂ .(H ₂ O) ₂	Brown	17.7 (17.5)	2.58
Cu ₂ (MPDTTC) ₂ .(H ₂ O) ₂	Brown	18.7 (18.7)	dia.
(VO) ₂ (PPDTTC) ₂ .(H ₂ O) ₂	Green	14.1 (14.8)	2.00
Co ₂ (PPDTTC) ₂ .(H ₂ O) ₂	Brown	16.5 (16.7)	4.54
Ni ₂ (PPDTTC) ₂ .(H ₂ O) ₂	Brown	16.4 (16.6)	2.00
Cu ₂ (PPDTTC) ₂ .(H ₂ O) ₂	Green	19.7 (19.7)	dia.

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses.

Magnetic properties :

The room temperature magnetic moment data (Table 1) show the oxovanadium(II), cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes to be paramagnetic. The μ_{eff} values show the presence of one, three and two unpaired electrons respectively, indicating the +4 state of V, and +2 state of Co and Ni. In the case of Co, the usual formation of a tris-chelate and oxidation to +3 state imparting a diamagnetic character to the complex do not take place. This may be due to the steric factor. Thus the ligands may force Co to remain in the +2 state. In the case of Ni^{II} complexes, the μ_{eff} values are lower than the expected ones (2.83 B.M.). This decrease may be due to the antiferromagnetic exchange between the two nickel atoms². The Cu^{II} complexes are diamagnetic suggesting a strong antiferromagnetic coupling interaction between the two copper centers through the ligands by the super-exchange mechanism. The diamagnetic character of the complexes indicates that the ground state is the singlet ($S = 0$) and the excited state is the triplet state ($S = 1$)³.

IR spectra :

The IR spectra of the ligands show $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ at 1458–1430, $\nu_{\text{CSS- (as)}}$ at 990–960 and $\nu_{\text{CSS- (s)}}$ at 692–680 cm^{-1} , showing the bidentate nature of the dithiocarbamato group⁴. In the complexes these bonds suffer negative shifts showing coordination of sulfur to the metal. This is further confirmed by $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$ at 390–360 cm^{-1} . The complexes, except those of VO^{II} show bands at 1610–1600 (δ_{OH}), 3450–3200 ($\nu_{\text{OH}} + \nu_{\text{NH}}$) and 380–370 cm^{-1} ($\nu_{\text{M-O}}$). These indicate the presence of coordinated water.

Electronic spectra :

The diffuse reflectance spectra of the VO^{II} complexes show maximum absorptions at 10526–15384, 16666 and

22222 cm⁻¹, which have been assigned to ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$, ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$ and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$ transitions, respectively, indicating C_{2v} local symmetry around vanadium⁵. The geometry may be square-pyramidal with respect to each vanadium. The magnetic susceptibility and the electronic spectral data do not indicate vanadium-vanadium interaction. The absence of this interaction may be attributed to the more electropositive character acquired by vanadium due to the more electro-negative oxygen atoms attached to them.

The Co^{II} complex of OPDTTC shows absorptions at 14285, 20000, 22222 and 33333 cm⁻¹, which are assigned to the transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$, respectively. The absorption at 33333 cm⁻¹ is assigned to cobalt-cobalt interaction⁶. The presence of two coordinated water molecules has already been confirmed by IR spectral data. Thus the local symmetry around each cobalt is octahedral considering the metal-metal interaction. The complexes of MPDTTC and PPDTTC have been assigned to distorted square-pyramidal geometry based on their absorptions. The former shows absorptions at 8200, 13333, 17800 and 22222 cm⁻¹, which are assigned to the transitions ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(F)$, ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4B_{1g}(F)$, ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(P)$ and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(P)$, respectively. The PPDTTC complex shows absorptions at 9523, 12500 and 22222 cm⁻¹, which are assigned to ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(F)$, ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4B_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(P)$ transitions, respectively. These transitions are characteristic of d^7 square-pyramidal system indicating very weak metal-metal interaction because of the increased distance between the two metal centers.

All the Ni^{II} complexes absorb at 9000–11111, 10000–11764, 10526–13333 and 20000–22222 cm⁻¹, which have been assigned to transitions ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3B_{2g}$, ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3A_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g(F)$ and ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3A_{2g}(P)$, respectively, indicating square-pyramidal geometry similar to the cobalt complexes.

The Cu^{II} complexes of OPDTTC and MPDTTC show absorptions at 22470–22520 cm⁻¹ indicating a square-planar geometry⁷. They also show absorptions at 23500 and 37000 cm⁻¹ indicating the binuclear copper(II) and dimeric structures⁸.

EPR spectra :

The VO^{II} complexes show eight lines ($I = 7/2$). This indicates that there is no vanadium-vanadium interaction. The Co^{II} complexes show EPR spectrum only at low temperature. Moreover, only a single peak is observed due to the effective spin, $S' = 1/2$. The Ni^{II} complexes give isotropic g value and the interpretation is difficult due to zero field splitting. However, the paramagnetic nature rules out the possibility of square-planar structure. Hence, the structure may be octahedral.

Conclusion :

The tetrathiocarbamate complexes are dimeric. The Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes have distorted octahedral structure with metal-metal interaction. The VO^{II} complexes have square-pyramidal structure without metal-metal interaction. The copper complexes are diamagnetic, while the others are paramagnetic. The interesting features are as follows. (i) the geometry of the cobalt complex forces cobalt to be present in the +2 state; otherwise, cobalt would have been oxidized from +2 to +3 state spontaneously during complexation, and (ii) the copper(II) complexes are diamagnetic due to antiferromagnetic coupling through super-exchange phenomenon.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of AnalaR grade and used as such.

Synthesis of ligands : A mixture of *o*-phenylenediamine (0.05 mol), barium hydroxide (0.05 mol) and carbon disulfide (0.11 mol) was dissolved in minimum quantity of acetone-water mixture (1 : 1) and stirred till a clear solution was obtained. The residue, if any, was filtered off. To the clear solution, ethanol was added to precipitate the barium salt of the ligand. The precipitate was dried, redissolved in water, filtering the residue, if any, and reprecipitated by adding alcohol to the filtrate. Similarly, *m*- and *p*-phenylenediaminetetrathiocarbamates of barium were synthesized.

Synthesis of complexes : The complexes were prepared *in situ*. To *o*-phenylenediamine (0.05 mol) dissolved in acetone, NaOH (0.1 mol) dissolved in minimum amount of water was added with stirring till a clear solution was obtained. VOSO₄·5H₂O (0.05 mol) was dissolved in minimum quantity of water and added to the ligand solution while stirring. The green colored complex formed was washed with water and acetone and dried under reduced pressure. The Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes were prepared similarly from the appropriate amounts of CoCl₂·6H₂O, NiCl₂·6H₂O and CuCl₂·2H₂O. The same procedure was followed to prepare the complexes of tetrathiocarbamates derived from *m*- and *p*-phenylenediamines.

C, H and N were estimated using Heraeus-Varlo-Erba 1108 analyzer. Sulfur was estimated gravimetrically as BaSO₄. The metal ions were estimated by adopting standard procedures.

Magnetic susceptibility was determined at room temperature by Gouy method using EM 50 type of Control Systems and Devices using Hg[Co(CNS)₄] as standard; necessary diamagnetic corrections were applied. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on Pye-Unicam SP and Perkin-Elmer

577 spectrophotometers, electronic spectra on AMINCO DW-2a, Varian-Cary 2390 and Perkin-Elmer 402 spectrophotometers, EPR spectra (at RT and LNT) on a Varian E-line, E-112 spectrometer operating at X-band frequency.

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